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“[L]ove the President personally”¹: The Abraham Lincoln-cult in Walt Whitman’s “O Captain! My Captain!” and John Ford’s *Young Mr. Lincoln*

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Abstract:

This paper considers Walt Whitman’s poem “O Captain! My Captain!” and John Ford’s film *Young Mr. Lincoln* to rethink the various nuances of the Abraham Lincoln-cult in American collective memory. The mythologisation of Abraham Lincoln aligns with the history of the American Civil War and the President’s complex relationship with the legislative abolition of slavery in the country. This paper will analyse the historical complexities of these phenomena vis-à-vis the figure of Abraham Lincoln, using Whitman’s poem and Ford’s film as points of reference to explore how American democracy created the cult of Lincoln to consolidate a variant of democratic understanding shaped by a sense of contested radicality. To achieve the same, the paper will closely examine both literary and cinematic texts, while also incorporating the heterogeneity of American history that underpin the mythologisation of President Lincoln.

Keywords: Abraham Lincoln, mythologisation, American Civil War, Abolition of Slavery, Collective Memory.

The Abraham Lincoln-cult in American Collective Memory

Abraham Lincoln’s famous “Gettysburg Address” of November 19, 1863, bore the promise of continuing the idea of liberty and the proposition that “all men are created equal”, which were the founding stones of the American nation. Lincoln showcased, through his typical blending of “feeling” with “condensed prose masterpieces” (Ferguson 698), the importance of taking the “unfinished work” of the dead soldiers forward so that their death does not remain a meaningless sacrifice, because history will not “long remember what we say here, but it can never forget what they did here” (Lincoln, “Gettysburg” 297). The “soulful tones” of Lincoln’s addresses, which are both intellectually powerful and sentimental, become manifestations of his “personal distress” (Ferguson 698). Arguably, as has been pointed out by many critics, the rhetorical genius of Lincoln, the orator, was significant in the process of Lincoln’s mythmaking.

The mythmaking of Abraham Lincoln, thereby the development of the Lincoln cult, is the primary concern of the present essay. Abraham Lincoln’s presence in the American imagination owes to his stand in the American Civil War (1861-1865). His emergence as a national hero and the rhetoric of American democracy are crucial themes in Walt Whitman’s elegy “O Captain! My Captain!”, as well as John Ford’s film *Young Mr. Lincoln* (1939). Traditionally, History is realised as the remembrance of great men, who are, in Antonio Gramsci’s words, the “new intellectuals”, actively participating in the day-to-day world as “constructor, organiser, “permanent persuader””, not simply functioning as “exterior and momentary mover of feelings and passions” (Gramsci 10), thereby leading to the development of “consent.” Now, Lincoln’s presence in the American collective memory is rather complex. Barry Schwartz finds the contradiction between strong leadership and a democratic society contributing to this complexity. He argues that as much as “[c]ommon, weak men cannot represent great and powerful nations”,

“elitist strongmen cannot represent democracies.” So, Lincoln’s image consisted of “stateliness, authority and dignity on the one hand” and “plainness, familiarity and homeliness on the other” (Schwartz, “Iconography” 301-2). Collective memory becomes an instrument of mythmaking. Here, a society’s past is very much determined by “individual remembering and forgetting” (Schwartz, “Iconography” 302). Memory functions as opposed to History. While the latter is a teleological reconstruction of the past, memory, being a non-Historical dialectic of remembering and forgetting, is “vulnerable to manipulation and appropriation,” and remains “unconscious of its successive deformations.” Also, the intensity of remembering is inconsistent due to its complex existence as something that is “dormant” with the possibility of being “periodically revived” (Nora 8).

Walt Whitman’s “O Captain! My Captain!”: Elegy and Mythmaking

These provide the premise for Walt Whitman’s poem. Written in response to the “foulest crime in history known in any land or age” (Whitman, “This” 285), i.e., the assassination of Abraham Lincoln, “O Captain! My Captain!” explores and recreates this mythmaking tradition. Whitman exploits an oft-used political metaphor of the ship and the captain to show that the American democracy, the history of which was “unwritten” and “yet to be enacted”, has lost its messiah. As he proposes, American democracy was then in an “embryo condition” (Whitman, “Democratic” 765). “O Captain! My Captain!”, written in 1865,² is Walt Whitman’s least characteristic (also, weak) – he makes a conscious use of stanza divisions, rhyme and meter to reach a larger audience –, highly popular and one of the most anthologised poems. Whitman once, in mild irritation, observed that he is “almost sorry” that he “ever wrote the poem” (Killingsworth 64).

The poem in question is an elegy, a “formal and sustained poem of lament for the death of a particular person” (Abrams 45). Elegy functions as a literary ritual, where the ritualistic act of mourning is substituted by a symbolic expression of grief through poetic form. Mourning, contrary to melancholia, is a process of healing. It occurs with the realisation of the no-longer-existence of the “loved object.” This non-existence “proceeds to demand that all libido shall be withdrawn from its attachments to the object.” Therefore, mourning is a work that involves a “great expense of time and cathartic energy” (Freud 20-1). Mourning is essentially a public activity. According to the fact sheet developed by the National Resource Center for Crisis Nurseries and Respite Care Services, funded by the US Department of Health and Human Services, mourning is a “grief gone public” (Lutz 222). The elegist in this poem is preoccupied with the act of mourning. There is an “unwillingness” to “give up the dead” by “continuing [the] relationship between the dead and the living” (Kennedy 57). Alongside mourning, what is evident in this poem is the act of celebrating the person who is no more. Such an act of celebration contributes to the development of the hero cult. The elegist has achieved this through certain strategies. Whitman ceases to provide any historical reference to the *act* of Lincoln’s assassination, albeit using a metaphoric reference to the activity. Peter Doyle, a close friend of Walt Whitman, was an eyewitness to the tragedy. He described the events of that evening – the muffled gunshot, his initial ignorance of the happenings, his inexplicable feelings after coming to know of the fact from Mrs. Lincoln’s cries “The President is shot!” (Murray 15). Whitman consciously attempted to eliminate the historical references from the poetic discourse to elevate Lincoln to a mythical figure. The historical character is rescued from the confinement of time and space. The moment the character moves beyond time and space, the hero is born. Abraham Lincoln, in the poem, is foregrounded as a mythological hero. Elegy portrays the death of the

subject as ironic, i.e., the person who is dead does not deserve it. An unbridgeable gap exists between the possibility and the reality – what the person could have been and the “dust” he has been reduced to. This overwhelming sense of wastefulness complements the process of cult formation. This process is quintessential to the composition of an elegy and the formation of the hero cult. Such an irony is explicitly delineated in the poem through the juxtaposition of two contrasting images – the lively “swaying mass” with “eager faces” waiting with “bouquets and ribbon’d wreaths” and the “pale and still” image of the “father” or “captain.” Whitman, on October 31 1863, wrote (in his diary) that he had found the “face & manner” of the President “inexpressively sweet” after his visit to the White House. The poet is mesmerised by the beauty of the President. Whitman went on to write that “I love the President personally” (qtd. in Pollak 159). Furthermore, “O Captain! My Captain!” ends with a reversed image. The enigmatic image of the President in 1863 had turned “cold and dead” in 1865. The “inexpressively sweet” face is marked by “pale and still” lips. The hands which held his friend’s shoulder and hand do not “feel” the speaker’s arm. The captain has “no pulse nor will.” The poem is overwhelmed with the terribly ironic situation.

John Ford’s *Young Mr. Lincoln*: The Mythical Lincoln in Depression Era Hollywood

The historical context of the emergence of Abraham Lincoln’s almost mythical presence corresponds with that of the American Civil War. Lincoln’s importance in American imagination is due to his position as a propagator of equality and liberty through the abolition of slavery. Arguably, the Emancipation Proclamation (1863) is his most significant contribution to American history. Still, his political position as a mass leader is worth debating. The Missouri Compromise (1820) was an important measure against slavery. Nevertheless, it was not much effective given the various conflicting fugitive slave laws and personal liberty laws which were

in function. This was followed by several conservative measures and pro-slavery developments, of which the Kansas-Nebraska Act (1854) and the Dred Scott v. Sandford case (1857) are worth mentioning. These events paved the way for the emergence of Abraham Lincoln in the American political sphere. In the historic address at the Illinois Republican Convention, Springfield on June 17, 1858, Abraham Lincoln declared that a “half slave and half free” government cannot last – “A house divided against itself cannot stand.” He traces the hands of the “workmen” – Stephen A. Douglas, Franklin Pierce, Roger B. Taney and James Buchanan – as conspirators, who cryptically “worked upon a common plan”, in the adroit formulation of “the Nebraska Doctrine and the Dred Scott decision” (Lincoln, “The” 82-4). Lincoln strongly condemned the pro-slavery forces. Although his position as an abolitionist remains debatable, in the Presidential election of 1860, there was “too strong an aroma of abolitionism” (Guelzo 401) for the Republicans. Abraham Lincoln’s debates with the pro-slavery figures, especially Stephen Douglas, reveal his stature as an emancipator of the slaves.

John Ford’s *Young Mr. Lincoln* (1939) makes use of the ideological rivalry between the two leaders, although this is not central to the film’s narrative. John Ford’s film paints the making of Abraham Lincoln. Here, the “daguerrotypes ... with vital breath [are] brought to life” (Eisenstein 141). *Young Mr. Lincoln* was made in 1939 – a turbulent year marking the end of the Great Depression and the beginning of World War II. The image of Abraham Lincoln was significant in the Depression-era Hollywood films. His image inspired the citizens to get united at a time when people were losing faith in American democracy, so the Lincoln Memorial turned into a recurrent motif to showcase democratic values through cinema (Stokes 214-5). Ford’s experiments with American history allowed an “[urgent reexamination of] national values” (McBride 269). The intensity of a John Ford film lies in the relation between “the aesthetics of

the cinematic text and the contexts of American culture and character” leading to the development of a “democratic aesthetic” which marked the standards of the “Hollywood Renaissance” (Girgus 22, 24). *Young Mr. Lincoln* is not a typical portrayal of Lincoln during the Depression years, representing the President’s complex struggle against or the famous addresses at Gettysburg or Springfield. John Ford’s film is more anecdotal than historical. There have also been several conscious deviations from the historical facts. John Ford, Lamar Trotti (screenwriter) and Darryl F. Zanuck (producer; 20th Century Fox) attempted to represent the man through his shyness and follies. In one of the scenes, Lincoln is “so lithe and graceful that no one in the dance cares he’s the only one not in white tie” (Gallagher). For a long time, the film had been dismissed by the critics for its historical inaccuracy. Mark S. Reinhart observes that the film is “a decidedly unsatisfying Lincoln screen biography” (Reinhart 222).

However, to argue *Young Mr. Lincoln* from historical and biographical perspectives is only to reduce the enormous possibilities of the film. It is also inadequate to forget the system within which Ford was making his masterpiece – the classical Hollywood. Melodrama was a staple of classical Hollywood. Although *Young Mr. Lincoln* does not show much loyalty towards historical facts, it successfully fulfils in communicating with American democracy and culture, thereby contributing to a reading of history itself. Melodrama is defined by its *excess*. Melodrama allows for “possibilities in the impossible” (Goldberg 156) where “an exciting, excessive, parabolic story” is constructed, leading to the “creation of drama” (Brooks 2). Peter Brooks argues that the “melodramatic mode” articulates the “moral occult”. It is a space of “operative spiritual values which is [*sic*] both indicated within and masked by the surface of reality” (5). This deviation from the historical genre to the “melodramatic mode” upholds the mythmaking process of Abraham Lincoln. J.E. Smyth, in her essay “*Young Mr. Lincoln*: between

myth and history in 1939,” meticulously explains the various misreadings of the film, which have focused primarily on its historical inaccuracy. One of the important deviations in the film is the central murder case. Historians have misinterpreted the film as “a historical travesty and folksy perversion” of Lincoln’s 1858 William ‘Duff’ Armstrong Murder Trial (193). The Armstrong murder trial was changed to the murder trial of the Clays. Though the basic instrument of the resolution was the same – Farmer’s Almanac³ – the nitty-gritty of the trial was different. The screenwriter metaphorically made the murder occur on an Independence Day and the trial earlier in Lincoln’s career. In a celebrated analysis of the film, *Cahiers Du Cinema* attempted to point out the ideological underpinnings of the film and argued that the film has been dehistoricised to present a “moralising discourse” where history is sustained through a “specific repetition”, through an “anticipation” or “predestination” of “future [being] contained in the past” (15). Throughout the film, Lincoln searches for “what’s right and what’s wrong,” beyond earthly law, a law of a higher order. So, there is an underlying conflict between “individual greatness and the rule of law” and the tension is “heightened “given “the demo’s passion for equality” (Brogdon 8). After Lincoln’s unprecedented win in the murder trial, the process of mythmaking in the film takes a crude form through the use of images and sound. This can be imagined as a moment of elevation from “innocence” to “experience”. The makers are in a constant process of reevaluation of “the difference between the real, ‘historical’ Lincoln and the myth in American consciousness” (Smyth 200). As the film ends with Lincoln’s “experience” – Lincoln walking towards the landscape in a static medium shot and the shot dissolving to the Lincoln Memorial – “a rare degree of pathos” is captured (Eisenstein 141). After walking out of the court, winning the case, Lincoln faces the cheering crowd. That is the moment when the man becomes a myth. And the process of mythmaking is completed when, in the last scene, the

Lincoln Memorial is shown with “Glory! Glory! Hallelujah!” playing in the background. There are several other ways through which the mythmaking works, e.g., Rosemary Benet’s verse in the epigraph. Nancy Hanks’ last interrogation hints towards a “sacrificial, Christ-like dimension to her son’s destiny” (Paquet-Deyris). The moment of transition from the cinematic narrative to the Lincoln Memorial captures the image of the landscape. The film, therefore, no longer confines itself to the to-be President and its mythmaking but seizes “the ethos and the pathos of the republic” (Gorin). The figure need not necessarily be “at the center of the frame for a film to exist” (Gorin). This contributes to the greater project of the American dream, informing the works of both Walt Whitman and John Ford with Abraham Lincoln as the central character of American democracy.

John Ford’s association with the American dream lies in the re-exploration of the American culture through the enormous use of landscapes, a hallmark of John Ford’s lifelong engagement with the genre of Western. Even in *Young Mr. Lincoln*, not technically a Western, the landscape is given enormous importance throughout. The landscape becomes a myth *per se*, aiding the representation of “the ethos and the pathos” of America. Walt Whitman, on the other hand, places Lincoln at the centre of his poetic discourse to commemorate all those people lost in the war and to memorialise the survival of the Union through the celebration of Lincoln (Killingsworth 63). In a letter to Nathaniel Bloom and John F.S. Gray, on March 19, 1863, Whitman observes that he finds a “supernatural tact” in Lincoln’s attempt to “[keep] the ship afloat.” He goes on to observe that “never yet captain, never ruler, had such a perplexing, dangerous task as his” (“Walt”). This letter interestingly uses the same metaphor as the Lincoln elegy in question. Emphasis on the multidimensional difficulties of the subject opens up the possibilities for projecting him as a hero. Though there is an undercurrent of hero worship, the

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adjectives “perplexing” and “dangerous” can be historically validated. Historically speaking, Lincoln’s position was perplexing in the sense that he was unable to put an end to slavery. Referring to the Lincoln-Whitman correspondence, Allen Grossman argues that for the poet “perceptibility of his world” is recovered through the “establishment of difference between the living and the dead” and for Lincoln, the move towards the emancipation of slaves initiated “the difference between persons and things” (Grossman 887). The Emancipation Proclamation (January 1, 1863) clearly stated that “all persons held as slaves within said designated States and parts of States are, and henceforward shall be, free” (Lincoln, “Emancipation” 216).

Conclusion: The Mythical Lincoln’s Contested Radicality

A century after this incident, in one of the most remarkable speeches of American history, Martin Luther King Jr. said that “Five score years ago a great American in whose symbolic shadow we stand today signed the Emancipation Proclamation.” Rightly, the act of issuing the Proclamation was Lincoln’s most significant work, but, as King Jr. goes on to speak, the African-Americans are still not free and their assemblage was “to cash a check” on which (“promissory note”) “America has defaulted” (King). This proves Lincoln’s task as “perplexing, dangerous.” Barry Schwartz, who has rigorously worked on the image of Lincoln in the American imagination⁴, observes that Lincoln’s esteem faced a gradual decline from the 1920s. The man who was given five distinct images of “Saviour of the Union”, “Great Emancipator”, “Man of the People”, “First American”, “Self-made Man” (Schwartz, “Abraham” 3) lost his reputation in the collective memory, beginning from the years of Great Depression. Therefore, the mythologised Lincoln became a recurrent motif in the then Hollywood.

Both Walt Whitman and John Ford execute a similar process of mythmaking. Though they attempt to place their subject beyond time for a successful rendition of the mythological narrative, since they operated under a historical system, the underlying knowledge structures in the unconscious shaped their form of representation. Therefore, the mythmaking in both “O Captain! My Captain!” and *Young Mr. Lincoln* is a product of the historical developments of the different periods in which Walt Whitman and John Ford, respectively, have worked.

Endnotes:

1. In 1863, Walt Whitman wrote, "I love the President personally". These writings were later collected in Whitman's *Notebooks and Unpublished Prose Manuscripts*, edited by Edward F. Grier, 6 vols., New York UP, 1961-77. Quoted in J.R. LeMaster and Donald D. Kummings, editors. *Walt Whitman: An Encyclopedia*. Garland Publishing, 1998. Reprinted in https://whitmanarchive.org/criticism/current/encyclopedia/entry_280.html.
2. The poem was first published in the *New York Saturday Press*, November 4, 1865. Later, it was anthologised in the *Drum-Taps* “Sequel”, *Passage to India* (1871, 1876) with several revisions. Finally, it was collected in the “Memories of President Lincoln” segment of *Leaves of Grass* (1881). See Walt Whitman, *Leaves of Grass and Other Writings*, edited by Michael Moon, W.W. Norton & Company, 2002, pp. 284; Gregory Eiselein, ““O Captain! My Captain!” [1865].” *Walt Whitman: An Encyclopedia*, edited by

J.R. LeMaster and Donald D. Kummings, Garland Publishing, 1998. Reprinted in https://whitmanarchive.org/criticism/current/encyclopedia/entry_40.html.

3. The Abigail Clay case in the film is based on the real William “Duff” Armstrong Murder Trial (1858). Mark S. Reinhart writes, “Armstrong was the son of Jack and Hanna Armstrong, Lincoln’s old friends from New Salem. He was accused of murdering a man after a religious camp meeting held at Virgin’s Grove, Illinois, in August 1857. Lincoln took on Armstrong’s case at Hanna’s request, and charged the Armstrongs no fee for his services.” Lincoln had won that murder trial using a similar strategy as shown in the film. He referred to the *Farmer’s Almanac*. The moon was very low during the act of murder. So, Lincoln proved that the “prosecution’s star witness” was lying regarding the bright moonlight. This led to his client’s acquittal. See Mark S. Reinhart, *Abraham Lincoln on Screen: Fictional and Documentary Portrayals on Film and Television*, 2nd ed., McFarland & Company, 2009, pp. 221.

4. Two of Barry Schwartz’s most important books on this subject are *Abraham Lincoln and the Forge of National Memory* (2000) and *Abraham Lincoln in the Post-Heroic Era* (2008). While the former deals with the growth of Lincoln’s fame till World War I from his death, the latter work traces the decline of his fame from the 1920s onwards.

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Filmography

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